

The Universe: A Perfect Network?

Mathematically speaking, from the circle passes an infinite number of lines. Using that analogy, where a particle is represented by a circle and a “communication pathway” is represented by a line, we can describe this particular “network”.

Does the mathematical analogy theoretically prove that every particle communicates **directly** with every other particle in the Universe, thus making it a perfect network?

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